

Angelo Leogrande¹

Low Pay Employees in the Italian Regions

Central Italy is the geographical area with the lowest presence of low-wage workers among the Italian macro-areas.

Istat in 2019 calculates the value of low-paid employees. Low-wage employees are defined as the “Percentage of employees with an hourly wage lower than 2/3 of the median of the total number of employees”.

Ranking of regions by value of low-paid employees in the Italian regions. In first place in the ranking of low-paying employees in 2019 is Calabria with a value of 21%, followed by Campania with a value of 17.4% and Sicily with a value of 17.3%. Molise is in ninth place with a value of 9.5% of low-paid workers, followed by Umbria with a value of 8.9% and Piedmont with a value of 8.1%. Friuli Venezia-Giulia closes the ranking with a value of 6.1%, Lombardy with a value of 5.7%, and Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount equal to 4.8%.

The ranking of the regions by variation of low-paid workers in the transition between 2008 and 2019. If we look at the value of the variation in the value of low-paid workers in the transition between 2008 and 2019, then it is possible to verify that there are losers and winners. Losers are those regions where the value of low-paying workers has grown. Winners are those regions where the value of low-income workers has decreased. Among the losers there are Sicily, in first place, with a value of 1.8%, Valle d'Aosta in second place with a value of 1.00%, Veneto and Calabria with a value of 0.3%, Liguria with a value of 0.2%, and Umbria with a value of 0.1%. Among the winners in first place there is Molise with a value of -2.5%, followed by Sardinia with -2.4% and the Marche with a value of 2.00% and to follow the other regions with values included between -1.0% and -0.1%.

North. The value of the percentage change of low-paid workers decreased in Northern Italy from 2015 to 2019 from a value of 7.2% to an amount of 6.4% or equal to a value of -0.80 units equal to at a value of -11.11%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016, the value of low-paid workers went from a value of 7.5% to a value of 6.5% or equal to a variation of -0.70 units equal to a value of -9.72%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of workers with low pay in the North increased from a value of 6.5% to a value of 6.75 or equal to a change of 0.20 units equal to a value of 3.08%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of low-paid workers remained constant at 6.7%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of low-paid workers went from a value of 6.7% to a value of 6.4%.

Center. The value of the change in the percentage of low-paid workers decreased between 2015 and 2019 from an amount equal to 10.7% to a value of 9.2% or a reduction of -1.50 units equal to -14.02%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of the percentage change of workers with low pay in the Center decreased from a value of 10.7% to a value of 10.1% or equal to a change of -0, 60 units equal to a value of -5.61%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the percentage of low-paid workers decreased from a value of 10.1% to a value of 9.3% or equal to a change of -0.80 units equal to a value of -7.92%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the percentage of low-paid workers decreased from a value of 9.3% to a value of 9.1% or equal to a value of -0.20 equal to at a

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

value of -2.1%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019, the value of low-paid workers increased from a value of 9.1% to a value of 9.2% or equal to a value of 0.10 units equal to a value of 1.10%.

Southern Italy. The percentage of workers with low pay in Southern Italy decreased from a value of 17.2% in 2015 to a value of 16.2% in 2019 or a variation of -1.00 units equal to a value of - 5.81%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016, the value of low-paid workers increased from a value of 17.2% to a value of 17.6% or equal to a value of 0.40 units equal to a value of 2.33%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of workers with low pay in the South decreased from a value of 17.6% to a value of 17.5% or equal to a change of -0.10 units or equal to a value of -0.57%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of workers with low pay decreased from a value of 17.5% to a value of 17.4% or equal to a change of -0.10 units equal to a value of - 0.57%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019, the value of workers with low paychecks decreased from a value of 17.4% to a value of 16.2% or equal to an amount of -1.20 units equal to a value of 6.90%.

Clusterization. The k-Means algorithm [2] was used to verify whether the distribution of regions with low-paid workers tends to converge with the classification of Italy into macro-regions. There are therefore 3 clusters composed as follows:

- C1: is the cluster that has a higher value of low-wage workers made up of Calabria, Campania, Puglia and Sicily;
- C2: is the cluster with an intermediate value of low-wage workers made up of Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Liguria, Lombardy, Marche, Piedmont, Tuscany, Trentino Alto Adige, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta, Veneto;
- C3: is the low-value cluster of low-wage workers made up of Abruzzo, Basilicata, Lazio, Molise and Sardinia.

The value of clustering clearly shows that the SOUTH, with the exception of Basilicata, ranks first in terms of the value of low-paid workers. Contrary to expectations, the North is instead in the second intermediate cluster. While it is the center, with the addition of Basilicata and Sardinia, which has the lowest value of low-wage workers. Clustering, therefore, is counterfactual with respect to current views on wages in the NORTH and confirms the idea that in recent years it has been the Center that has maximized the benefits of growth compared to both the North and the South.

Machine Learning and Predictions. The dataset was used to estimate the amount of low-paid workers in 2019 compared to previous years with a predictive model and with a machine learning system with a learning rate of 95%. The results show that the “Gradient Boosting”, “Adaboost” and “Tree” models are more efficient in terms of error reduction and R-squared.

Conclusions. In summary, it should be considered that on average 9 out of 100 Italian workers have low wages and this value reaches up to 16 in the South. Obviously the real value is even higher as it does not take into account illegal workers and the many who in the informal economy accept much lower incomes than those reported by ISTAT-BES.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l. and prof. Alberto Costantiello and Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

References

Leogrande, Angelo. Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. No. 112801. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2022.

Leogrande, Angelo. The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. No. 112954. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2022.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). *The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019* (No. 110814). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective Well-Being in Italian Regions: A Panel Data Approach. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551666>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Risk of Poverty in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6194023>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Employment Rate in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6211793>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Duration of Civil Proceedings in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6188615>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Reduction of NEETs in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6212291>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Social Participation in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6212069>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Crowding of Prisons in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395200>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590380>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591151>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484049>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Multichronicity in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591360>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*, <https://ilsudest.it/>. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590870>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591546>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Road Accidents in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590888>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Excess Weight in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635645>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636122>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6661189>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6743234>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Graduates in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6790391>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Income Gap Between Northern and Southern Italy. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013650>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Clustering and Prediction of the Employment Rate in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013660>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Reduction of the Perception of Employment Insecurity in the Italian Regions between 2013 and 2019. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013700>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Satisfaction for the Work in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013706>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Worsening of the Condition of Women Employed with Preschool Children in the Italian Regions in the Period 2015-2019. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013718>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Reduction of Fatal Accidents and Permanent Disabilities in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013737>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Non-Regular Employees in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013745>

